

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF SOKOTO STATE UNIVERSITY ON ITS HOST COMMUNITIES WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE TO MADORAWA VILLAGE

By

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Abstract

The study investigates socio-economic impact of Sokoto State University on Madorawa Village, Sokoto. The study also examines the nature of the socio-economic relationship between Sokoto State University and Madorawa Village. The study examines the extent Sokoto State University has influenced socio-economic activities in Madorawa Village. In order to meet the objectives of the study, the researcher employs a qualitative research method for data collection. A population of 20 respondents was drawn in the study area as the population of the study. Key informant interview was used. It was recommended that there is the need for Sokoto State Government to consider developing the area infrastructural of SSU on the other hand, should consider providing corporate social responsibility to the area in addition to its services to Madorawa Village and Primary health care centre etc. This would benefit both the indigenes of the area and members of the university community as well.

Introduction

The formation of the Sokoto State University is a blessing to the Madorawa village which is one of the immediate communities to the University. One such development is in the area of socio-economic development. Another area is in the area of employment generation which has been estimated to employ many members of their community.

Intent and Objectives of this Paper

The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. It analyzes the nature of the socio-economic relationship between Sokoto State University and Madorawa Village.
- ii. It tests the extent Sokoto State University has influenced socio-economic activities in Madorawa Village.

- iii. It studies the challenges confronting Sokoto State University, in its socio-economic relationship with Madorawa Village.
- iv. It provides recommendations for addressing socio-economic challenges.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

This introduces and discusses some literature relating to the work and at the same time it provides relevant theories that give the work theoretical backing.

A university is an institution of higher or tertiary education and research which awards academic degrees in various academic disciplines. Universities typically provide undergraduate teaching and graduate education (Aronowitz, 2000). The word “university” is deduced from the Latin “universitasmagistorum et-scholarium” which roughly stands for a community of teachers and students. While some universities had existed in Africa and Asia, the modern university system has roots in the European Medieval University, which was created in Italy and developed from Christian Cathedral schools for the clergy during the High Middle Ages (Barrow, 1990). The original Latin word “universitas” refers in general to a number of persons associated into one body, a society, company, community, guild, corporation, etc. at the time of the emergence of urban town life and medieval guilds,

specialized associations of students and teachers with collective legal rights usually guaranteed by charters issued by princes, prelates, or the towns in which they were located came to be denominated by this general term (Barrow, 1990). From this onset one can infer that, location and/or formation of a university is linked to its host community. I can understand that, even legal rights and charters establishing a university has to come from towns and princes or prelates in town it is situated. According to Diamond (1992) in modern usage, a University has come to mean, an foundation of higher education offering tuition in mainly non-vocational studies and typically holding the force to confer degrees. An important idea in the definition of a University is the notion of academic freedom. The first documentary evidence of this comes from the early life of the University of Bologna, which assumed an academic charter, the “Constitution Habita” in 1158 or 1185 which guaranteed the right of a travelling scholar to unhindered passage in the pursuits of education. Today, this is taken as the root of academic freedom. This is now widely recognized internationally under the “Magna Charta Universitatum.” From this writing it could be understood that without the guarantee of security from host communities, Universities could hardly run. Pedersen (1997) observed that, during medieval Europe, rulers and city governments began to create Universities to satisfy a European thirst for knowledge, and the opinion that

society would gain from the scholarly expertise generated from these establishments. Princes and leaders of city governments perceived the potential benefits of delivering a scholarly expertise, develop with the ability to address difficult problems and reach desired goals.

Universities all over the world benefits from host communities much like host communities benefit from them. The University plays a key function as a gateway for the city and the area. Alumni who render to their homes can act as informal ambassadors, recommending that friends and family attend the University. A University can attend every bit a great neighbor. The shock of a university in its community goes beyond its economic impact and the skills its graduates contribute to the region's labor force (Ruegg, 2004). A University works to broaden participation in higher education, providing chances for all, especially students from its host community, whose parents or household may have lower socio-economic backgrounds. In another dimension, a University's facilities provide benefits to pupils, staff and the local community. In some instances, the caliber of the amenities offered cannot be matched in cities (Ruegg, 2004). The comportment of a University generates significant economic benefits for local and larger state economies. It answers this directly and indirectly. A University could impact on a local economy in the five following ways:

- i. The actions of the university
- ii. The subsistence spending of students who would need consumables and hostel/housing facilities.
- iii. The expenditure of visitors who travel to the University Academic Conferences or gatherings.
- iv. The impact the university's capital spending on infrastructural development which would create employment opportunities and;
- v. The university's spending on corporate social responsibility projects.
- vi. Heterogeneity of persons and cultures (cultural inclusiveness and knowledge spread).

The Nature of Socio-Economic Relationship between Universities and the Host Community

The predominant discourse, familiar since at least since the 1990s till date has emphasized the Tertiary institutions place as a main actor in a global system increasingly driven by knowledge, information and thoughts. We exist in a time when knowledge is ever more critical to our societies and economic systems in a world of rapidly circulating capital and people and of revolutionary communication technologies. Knowledge is replacing other resources as the primary driver of economic development, social Integration and

Cohesion and education have increasingly become the groundwork for individual prosperity and social mobility. Tertiary institutions engender broader Socio-economic growth as good as individual success.

It is a recognized fact that Tertiary institutions contribute to the growth and progress of the fellowship and attend the community which hosts them in holding a popular voice in the operation of globalization (Ali, 2010). The position of any institution in a community has been identified to be of outstanding value to the overall growth of an arena. Location impact, therefore means the influence of a new idea or institution in an area (that is, the environment), this new idea or concept can be in the shape of an institution of tertiary institutions encouraged by a state, regional or federal setting. In recent times, there has been a great deal of arguing around the location of tertiary institution in one town or the other. This is because people understand the fact that the location of such in an area or community could enhance rapid development of such areas Socio-economic (Argo, 2005). The naming of a tertiary psychiatric hospital in a community will create employment opportunity for both the skilled and unskilled labor and this will in turn increase the population of the town as a outcome of people migrating into the township to look for work opportunities (Ayobami, 1977). It could also induce alterations in economic activities, modifications in building conditions and

practice in order to make out with the educational trends (Ekanem et al, 2015). Nigeria is a multicultural state formation with over 250 ethnic groups, it has 570 Tertiary institutions, whose responsibilities apart from its function as an educational institution been a teaching and research institution they perform a function that is beyond the realm of education (Ehinmowo and Eludoyin, 2010). They are highly significant financial and social institution in the Communities which they work, offering their Communities educational, research, economic,

According to Garlick and Ekanem and Okon (2015), the relationship between Tertiary institution and its community can be delineated in three different ways;

- i. It can be traced through the structural perspective as a berth in which Tertiary institutions are regarded as economic boosters,
- ii. Through the spatial perspective as the association with equity measures such as student placement
- iii. Through perspective which is founded on the appreciation of the importance of a part to the tertiary institution that are placed there.

However, (Brennan, et al, 2004), sees a tertiary institution and their role in local, regional and central development to be goofing around four basic themes, namely; the notion of centrality of a university; its meaning and purpose; its

mission and operations; and, its innovation agenda and new modes of governance. Therefore, higher institutions have always had an impingement on the local, regional and central development apart from producing trained and trained skilled labor; university research and innovation are frequently viewed as engines of development and regional development while peaceful coexistence gives priority. In effect, the character of universities in community development is to produce a sense of fairness for all souls inside that community.

Extent at which University Influence Socio-Economic Activities of their Located Society

Societies have witnessed different stages of human civilization centering around knowledge. Based on advancements in knowledge, societies have been changing, transitioning and transforming.

In a further attempt by Nasreen (2015) Oke, Oredipe et al (2012) in stressing the decisive function of universities in the maturation and advancement of the societies concluded that universities do not only make human resource necessary for development activities, but also initiate and contribute to change in social clubs. Isola (2017) in his study recommended that such transformation dynamics are very much hooked on how change is managed by the societies through higher training. From the, study it can be concluded that this bold initiative of Osun state government and

the proper management of the institution by the various administrations since 2007 has brought about significant improvement in the communities in part of the university, the community and the government, particularly in areas of health facilities, infrastructural development, increase in economic and other commercial activities,

Isola (2017) in his research titled “Socio-economic Impact of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria on Host Community: A Case Study of Osun State University”, revealed that the location of the university has led to an increase in the standard of living of people within these communities, bring the people closer to each other from various ethnic backgrounds and also brings about employment opportunities and harmonious coexistence to the people of the community. The findings further revealed a positive correlation and cooperative relationship between the institution and its communities, due to the cooperativeness of the indigenes, non-indigenes and both management and students of the institution. The study concluded that location of a tertiary institution in an area is a stimulus to the area’s rapid growth, provided the activities of such tertiary institution are well guided and monitored.

Ugwuka (2015), also concluded that; “No doubt, it has been fully established that the citing of Babcock has brought much fame and prominence to the once quiet town. The socio-economic

conditions and status has greatly improved since the institution was established. Apart from the fact that the community's banking services are now most reliant on the several banks on campus, the university renders educational facilities to indigent students in the town and its environs. Although, there may have been some misunderstanding between Babcock University and the community on land matters, yet, the advantages of what such communal land were used for far outweighs the disadvantages of its deprivation from the community.

The Challenges Confronting the University in its Socio-Economic Relationship with its Located Area

Universities have frequently been regarded as key institutions in the processes of social change and development. The most explicit role they have been allocated is the production of highly skilled labour and research output to meet perceived economic needs. But during periods of more radical change –which may certainly have at their heart far-reaching changes in the economy – universities and/or their constituencies have sometimes played no less an important role in helping to build new institutions of civil society, in encouraging and facilitating new cultural values, and in training and socialising members of new social elites (Badat 2001) The idea of the university as an instrument of societal change has found expression in varying ways in earlier modernising societies of

both democratic and authoritarian persuasions: the land-grant colleges in the USA, the part played by universities in the modernisation of Japan, the incorporation of the universities into the socialist project of the Soviet Union and the countries which patterned themselves on that model, are just three examples. The roles played by universities in modernisation projects are varied. It is important to distinguish between examples where the role of the university is largely autonomous and examples where the role is set firmly within state plans and control mechanisms. It is important to distinguish between universities that 'ignite' change, those that 'accelerate' existing change and those that 'block' change. It is important to distinguish between examples of planned and intended changes and examples of the unintended consequences which arise out of university based activities. And, as was noted earlier, it is important to be aware of the implications of the role(s) played by the university prior to the period of transformation (Brennan and Shah, 2000). A lot of the recent literature on the roles of universities in the processes of transformation and modernization has been given to be normative: focusing on what universities ought to be getting along and what is designed for them to be making out. The promises and dreams of politicians and policy schemes are accepted to be achievable realities. Where the focus of debate is not normative – and is based on empirical study of the workings of higher

education institutions –greater emphasis has been put upon the internal changes within institutions that have been brought about by broader societal changes. There have been a number of recent studies into the alterations taking place within universities, e.g. Clark (1998); Maassen, (1996); Kogan and Hanney, (1999); Sporn, (1999); Kogan et al, (2000). Contradictions abound, academic work appears to be buffeted by all kinds of outside powers. It is subjected to greater managerialism, greater instrumentalism, greater competition, fresh configurations of restraint and accountability, and thus along. And yet institutional autonomy is increasingly celebrated, especially in countries where for long it appeared to have been compromised (Brown, 2000). Moreover, a study for example, Henkel (2000) reports evidence of the continuing resilience of traditional academic cultures.

From Mexico to Kyrgyzstan, higher education systems are said to be in the processes of restructuring under the combined effects and constraints of local socio-political transformations and global forces associated with the move towards the ‘knowledge society’. If, as it is usually assumed, higher education lies at the core of the knowledge society, then universities are everywhere faced with challenges and problems “undoubtedly bound to alter the nature of the academic enterprise to a degree that today seems almost impossible” (Kwiek, 2001). Still, evidence from the contrasted environments of this project’s study

location seems to shout out for a degree of relativism. Changes have certainly occurred everywhere, but the shock of global movements on each national landscape and on local institutions has differed significantly from one nation to another, without necessarily affecting their very core and primary offices. Curriculum reform often featured among the first targets of regime change on educational systems around the globe. The experience of communist and post-communist European countries also shows how permeable this area is to external influences. It is thus an interesting angle of approach to a state’s capacity for response to – or anticipation of - external demands and pressures. The variegation of the public supply of higher education is well exemplified by the case of Mexico, where the procedure occurred during the 1990s: “The universities lost ground in the percentages of public sector enrollment (from 69.4% to 55% in the 90s). They were gradually challenged by 44 technical universities, 79 decentralized technological institutes and, since 2001, three polytechnic universities. Most of these “new” establishments were located in small urban centers. They gave rise to a more equitable spatial distribution of higher education opportunities, but did not contribute to decrease the stresses brought about by the insufficient enrollment capabilities of the public universities in the large cities, (Bremen, 2004). As a pattern, they reacted to the expectations of scholars from poor sectors, who were to a very large degree

the first generation to possess access to higher education. They offered students, whose parents could not afford to ship them to other cities, the opportunity to enter in their own place of abode. To date, however, that enhancement of opportunities has been a pricey one.” (Jorge, 2013; Cooper and Subotzky, 1999).

Theoretical Framework

From both the conceptual and empirical literature review, several sociological and/or theoretical constructs can be derived that is, theory of institutional political economy, utility theory, and so on but the major theoretical construct that is equally derived from the review and which is capable of pointing this study is the “social exchange theory”.

The Social Exchange Theory

It is a social psychological view that explains social change and stability as a process of negotiated exchanges between parties. The Social Exchange theory posits that human relationships are constituted by the utilization of a subjective cost-benefit analysis and the comparison of alternatives (Karen and Erick, 2006). The theory has roots in economics, psychology and sociology. The Social Exchange theory features many of the main assumptions found in rational choice theory and structural linguistics. It is also used quite frequently in the business world to apply a two sided, mutually contingent and

rewarding process involving transactions or simply exchange (Ekanen et al, 2015).

George (1961) defined social exchange as the exchange of natural process, tangible or intangible, and more or less rewarding or costly, between at least two individuals.

George (1961) stressed the private behavior of actors in interaction with one another. Although on that point are several modes of exchange, George focused his studies on dyadic exchange. Castells (2001) are known for combining their studies within the theory of the psychological concepts, the yoke and the small group.

Nonetheless, George (1961) sums up the organization in three propositions: success, stimulation, and deprivation-satiation proposition. They are further explained as follows:

- i. Success proposition: when one notices they are honored for their activities; they incline to replicate the activity;
- ii. Stimulus proposition: the more often a special stimulus has resulted in a reward in the past, the more probable it is that a soul will answer to it;
- iii. Deprivation-satiation proposition: the more often in the recent past a person has got a particular reward, the less valuable any further unit of that reward becomes (George, 1961). In his own part, Blau (2001) focused his writings on social

exchange theory more towards the economic and utilitarian perspective. His utilitarian focus encourages the theorist to look forth as in what they anticipated the reward would be in regards to their next social interaction. Emerson (2008) posited that, self-interest and independence are key attributes of social interchange. These are the basic phases of interaction when two or more actors have something of value to each other, and they have to resolve whether to exchange and in what quantity.

Thibaut and Kelley (1959) determine the mutual interdependence of persons as the fundamental problem for the field of societal conduct. They built up a theoretical framework based on the interdependence of workers. They also highlighted social implications of different kinds of interdependence, such as reciprocal control. Agreeing to their interdependence definition, outcomes are based on a combination of parties' efforts and mutual and complementary systems.

To this conclusion however, Ike (1974) regarded the social exchange as a social behavior that may ensue in both economic and societal issues. According to him, it is possible to observe social exchanges everywhere, not exclusively in market relations, but in relations between institutions. Social exchange process brings satisfaction when people receive reasonable returns for their outlays. Social exchanges involve a

connection with one another; it implies trust and not legal obligations; being more flexible and rarely involve explicit bargaining. And both parties in a social exchange take responsibility for one another and depend on each other.

The forces of the Social Exchange theory are as follows:

- i. It is pretty easy to interpret the universal rules of the theory because of its focus on price and reward as the ground of societal relationships.
- ii. Cognition of the theory aids in having more balanced relationships while also providing awareness of what an individual or social institution costs are to other masses.
- iii. It aids to see the cost and reward of relationships and also helps to predict how to maintain and nurture relationships.

The social exchange theory is applied because it would countenance for a fuller discernment of the costs and rewards of the special relationship that exists between Sokoto State University and Madorawa Village.

From the recap thus far, it could be interpreted that the location or establishment of a University and indeed any higher institution of scholarship has affected on its server or local community socio-economically. It could equally be interpreted that the relationship is a mutual and/or reciprocal one, with each

party benefitting from the social exchange

From the above theoretical postulations, one can note that the kinship between a university or higher institution of reading with its host or local community is more of a social exchange, which is rarely of explicit bargaining. Both of them derive benefits from the social interaction. Against this theoretical line, the social exchange theory would guide this study in explaining the socio-economic impact of Sokoto State University on Madorawa Village in Sokoto.

Data Presentation and Analysis on Socioeconomic Impact of SSU on Madorawa Village

This Section represents the phase at which master data on the socioeconomic impact of the Sokoto State University (SSU) on Madorawa Village, Sokoto, Nigeria is being introduced and examined. In this regard, the presentation and analysis of data would focus on key topics such as: establishing the socioeconomic relationship between SSU and Madorawa Village, the extent SSU has influenced socioeconomic activities in Madorawa Village, and the challenges confronted by SSU in its socioeconomic relationship with Madorawa Village.

The Physical location upon which they were anchored had unintended socio-economic consequences for Madorawa Village.

Data presentation

Twenty (20) key Informants provided information that helped substantiated the study. All of the key informants are males. Age bracket of these informants runs between 30 – 60 years. Two (2) out of the informants are staff of SSU; twelve (12) of the informants are students who are indigenes of Madorawa Village; the remaining eight (8) of the twenty informants are indigenes of Madorawa Village who had cause to interact with students and staff alike of SSU. These locals of Madorawa Village are traders with provision stores, land lords, and laundry men.

Nature of the Socio-economic Relationship between SSU and Madorawa Village

On this issue, the all Key Informants (2018) confirmed the existence of a Socio-economic relationship that exists in Madorawa Village by virtue of the location and establishment of SSU in the area. According to a student informant (2018):

“...there is no doubt that even when it is not listed on the objectives of the University, it is only natural for a Socio-economic relationship to exist between the two. Institutions of higher learning everywhere rely on their host communities for social reproduction; likewise, these host communities’ benefits in so many ways due to patronage of its economic goods and services...”

Other informants (2018) noted that, there are varieties of socio economic relations for instance, between Umaru Aliyu Shinkafi Polytechnic (formerly Sokoto State Polytechnic) with Rugar Waru Community: this is the case with Faru-Faru that is currently benefitting by virtue of the location of College of Administration, and a host of Secondary schools. To this end, Madorawa Village is not an exception. On the nature of the Socio economic relationship, one aspect stands out which has to do with cordiality. According to an indigene informant (2018):

“... Sofar so good, the relationship between SSU and Madorawa Village has been cordial when a socio exchanges between the two is considered. There have been no incidences of theft, armed robbery, cultism and rape like what obtains between institutions of higher learning and their host communities in the Southern Part of Nigeria...”

In another dimension, the key informants (2018) noted that SSU has not been proactive in the provision of direct socio-infrastructure projects like what obtains in the relationship between Sokoto State University Sokoto and its host communities. For instance, the University Management has provided job opportunity and free admission opportunity to their host communities especially Madorawa Village.

Nevertheless, informants (2018) who are indigenes of Madorawa noted that they welcomed the establishment of SSU in their village. Apart from the fact that, the name of their village has spread far and near, the establishment of the University has opened up the village to modern ideas. Because of the Madorawa Village, indigenes have enrolled into both primary and secondary schools with the view to gain both admission and employment as the case may be.

Also, indigenes of the area have gotten the opportunity to inter-mingle with students of not only their own tribes but from other tribes and even religion as well. One would therefore observe that, the location of SSU in Madorawa Village has enhanced not only modernity but cultural diffusion as well.

Some indigene key informants noted that;

“... the experience I have had with the students of Sokoto State University has changed the way I believed the people the southern part of Nigeria to be. I even thought that because of the different types of people that would come into our society we would begin to experience things such as robbery, cultism, rape and others. Fortunately to my surprise and delight that has not been the case because students of Sokoto State University that I have come into contact with have in most cases been cordial although not all are good...”

On the relationship between SSU and Madorawa , another indigene noted that;

“... The people of this village are happy that the government had decided to locate this university in our community, this is because our people have benefitted immensely in many areas like jobs and businesses among others. Some have gotten jobs like security guards cleaners, clerks while the others who set-up provision shops, food traders, barbers etc. have all seen their business grow and develop...”

Another indigene informant who supported this statement said:

“...During the initial establishment of Sokoto State University the traders in the town were very few but after just a few short years their numbers have significantly increased, the same could be said about those who build houses for rents, now there are numerous construction works going on in the village to provide accommodation for the students of Sokoto State University which has provided employment for the people of Madorawa.

While an indigenous student respondent noted that;

“...The university has not really made any effort in bringing infrastructural development to the village bet we believe that it will come in due time because even

without Sokoto State University actively trying to bring developmental changes to Madorawa , the community has been developing all the same...”

This goes to say that although Sokoto State University has not itself brought any projects to the town, but due to its existence alone people from outside the village have come and purchased land and also employed labour for the construction of buildings which in general has had a huge developmental effect on the village. A staff informant is of the view that:

“...Sokoto State University has itself not brought any projects but people from various places now place huge value on our lands at least much more than they used to which has made land prices go higher and for the individuals that have sold any pieces of their land they have made large gains (profits).

Socio-economic Influences of SSU on Madorawa Village

The establishment of SSU even if unintended would have socio economic impact on Madorawa Village. This is the case with virtually all institutions of learning, as they cannot exist independently of their host communities. According to Irene (2014):

“...Several communities see the multi... effect and pride in having higher educational institutions

located in their areas: for instance, the people of Ibadan took pride in the establishment of the University of Ibadan (U I) in their town. In turn, the University of Ibadan, being the first to be established in Nigeria and indeed beyond at the time, helped transformed Ibadan town from a local settlement to a city. Presently, many socio-economic activities have sprung around the Ibadan metropolis...”

Isola (2017) further buttresses that:

“... the nature of many higher institutions is such that their physical operations are locally based. Therefore, the establishment of a higher institution in a community could ensure the rapid development of that community socially, economically, and even politically. The establishment of a higher institution in a community leads to the creation of employment opportunities for both the skilled and unskilled labour. It could also cause areas in order to cope with the educational trends...”

On this issue, an indigenous key informant (2018) noted that prior to the establishment of SSU;

“...many economic activities and businesses were basically absent in Madorawa Village. Even with its strategic proximity to express road, lands and houses were not duly appreciated. Virtually no one was

ready to invest in the village. But following the announcement that the SSU would be established, people from far and near started purchasing lands and building houses with the view to rent them out to SSU has thus helped in changing the demographics and landscape of Madorawa ...”

Overall, the establishment of Sokoto State University has had a positive impact on the people and their community as a whole. According to a staff respondent

“... the establishment of the university has reduced the number of unemployed people in Madorawa and because the people here have lower educational qualification they have been given jobs such as guards, cleaners, messengers, clerks and others. The university has also given admissions to some of the youths so they have the opportunity to further their education...”

Among the respondents, the students noted that:

“...businesses are thriving in the community now that the university has been established with more people entering into business such as provision shops, food traders, sale of perishable food items etc. Every form of business which exists within the community has experienced growth especially those that meet the needs of the growing students’ population within the village...”

From the above it could be noted that the indigenes of Madorawa believe that they have benefitted immensely from the establishment of SSU in their community economically and the university has further served to encourage the people to send their children to schools so they can fully exploit the benefits afforded to them by the university.

An indigenous respondent when asked above the kind of services Sokoto State University renders to the community had this to say;

“... aside from the medical treatment the indigenes receive in the school clinic and also the jobs and admission for students of Madorawa , Sokoto State University does not have any other programmes/policies that directly impact on the lives of the people of Madorawa ...”

Another staff respondent indicates that:

“... I cannot say for sure, any particular social intervention programme that Sokoto State University has instituted in Madorawa Village. I don't believe that Sokoto State University as an organization, itself instituted any social programmes. From the above view of respondents, it could be summarized that the people of Madorawa believe that the changes that Madorawa Village has been experiencing from the time the university was established till date and has been an unintended

consequence of the university rather than any planned action on the part of the university...”

From the above it could be seen that if Sokoto State University takes a more active approach in influencing social developmental projects in Madorawa Village the speed and quality in which the socio-economic development witnessed could be faster and more qualitative than what currently exists.

Furthermore, Key Informant (2018) who is an indigene of Madorawa Village noted that:

“... Following the establishment of the SSU, indigenes of Madorawa have enjoyed employment opportunities: the school authority has allowed indigenes to be employed as security men, messengers and drivers...”

The above employment opportunities have enhanced the individual economies of indigenes of Madorawa working in SSU. The University has made it clear that it would continue to provide employment opportunities at both junior and senior cadres depending on the nature of qualifications at the disposal of indigenes of the area (key informants, 2018). It should however be noted that, indigenes of Madorawa do not have graduates with University degrees and other post – secondary school qualifications. It is for this reason that most of the indigenes working in SSU are workers of junior cadre. It is expected that the location of SSU in

Madorawawould serves as an educational booster.

While Madorawa Village do not currently have a graduate, some of the Key Informants (2018) noted that indigenes of the village are currently bracing up towards seeking for admissions in SSU. They noted that, the proximity of the University to the village makes it necessary for indigenes of the area to seek admission opportunities in SSU. They equally noted that apart from the employment opportunities the University has offered their people, it is yet to provide any infrastructure or direct services to the people of the area.

On whether the establishment of a University in Madorawahas been beneficial, the indigenous student Key Informant (2018) noted that:

“...the establishment of SSU has been and continue to be beneficial in so many ways. In the area of landed properties, indigenes of the area have acquired new lay outs for the purpose of building provision stores, shops and houses for rental to students and staff of the University...”

Not only in the area of landed properties and houses for rent, has the establishment of SSU helped to change the cultural and social world view of the people of Madorawa Village. Before the influx of students into the area, indigenes of Madorawahave a negative and/or Sceptical view about University

education. To them, the word “Yan-Boko” is used to refer to students as westerners.

In other words, these students are nominal Muslims and members of the larger society; they are acculturated with foreign ideas. While the preceding sceptic outlook may not be far from the truth, the presence of students within Madorawahave made indigenes to experience a sort of ‘‘cultural diffusion’’. Some of them now understand some of the tribes and religion of students in the area. They have equally understood that being in a University does not make students nominal Muslims or members of the society (Key Informant Interview, 2018).

Politically, the continued interaction of students from SSU with indigenes of Madorawa , has led to a growing wave of awareness. This is because; some of these students who are from urban and cosmopolitan areas are helping to make indigenes understand that they have certain demands to make on the government at all levels. Just as they have obligation to the government (State, Local and Federal), they have rights (Political, Economic and Social) to benefit from the government also (KII, 2018). It should however be noted that the political awareness is still at its embryonic stage in the area; it is yet to translate into a movement that would draw the attention of the government towards the socio-economic development of the area.

On the area of health, the Key Informants (2018) noted that:

“... the University has not directly established any health facility in Madorawa . Perhaps, it is quite imperative to mention here that the clinic in the school is not discriminatory to patients of Madorawaarea...”

It should be noted that, the workers of SSU who happen to be indigenes of Madorawa , are instructive in extending the health services of SSU to the area. It suffices to mention here that, while the school clinic is not adequately equipped with human and material resources, it has gone a long way to assuage some of the health complications of indigenes of Madorawawho happen to seek its services.

On the issue of housing, the Key Informants (2018) noted that:

“...students and Staff expenditure has impacted positively on the local economy of Madorawa . Apart from the houses for rent, the spending of students in other related areas are positive also. Because students are renting houses, it become imperative to seek the services of local carpenters, local electricians, local plumbers, local water vendors, and local laundry services among others...”

“However, because of the proliferation of houses and apartments for rent, many land lords have to change many of their building structures” (Key Informant Interview, 2018). To this end, one could understand that the presence of SSU generates significant economic benefits for Madorawaand even larger economy of Sokoto economy, SSU have continued to impact on the local economy of Madorawain the following ways:

- i. The activities of the University. For instance, when the University matriculates its students, it attracts small scale businesses like food vendors, water vendors and so on;
- ii. The subsistence spending of students who would need consumables and housing facilities;
- iii. The spending of visitors who visit the University whenever there is any academic or political gathering in the school; and
- iv. The impact of the University’s capital spending on infrastructural development in the school which has continued to create employment opportunities i.e. hiring of local services of bricklayers/labourers, masons, carpenter’s etc.

Challenges in the Socio-economic Relationship between SSU and Madorawa Village

Like any other relationships, there is bound for parties to experience some

challenges the indigenous Key Informants (2018) noted;

“... the Socio-economic relationship between SSU and Madorawa Village has been cordial and reciprocal. There has been no report of violence against each other. Both students and indigenes of the village have been going about their businesses unmolested...”

Nevertheless, indigenous Key Informants (2018) who are indigenes of Madorawa Village raised the issue of adequate compensation for the land used in establishing SSU. According to the Key Informants (2018):

A large chunk of people need to relocate to hinterland of Madorawaso that the University could be established. This relocation was anchored on the promise of both land and financial compensation to take care in conveniences suffered in the process of the relocation. To this day only land was provided to us. With these grievances on, it is imperative for the Sokoto State Government to honour its promise to the villagers.

On a general note, the Key Informants (2018) posited that, the University should try and register its presence in Madorawa Village by attracting infrastructural development in the village. It would benefit not only indigenes of the area but students of the University who are residents also.

Most indigenous and student respondents when asked about the area where the university could do more for the people of Madorawawere of the view that:

“...the university should put a more conscious effort into creating programs and policies that could bring faster development to the community, because as it is now the university could more than it currently is...”

Another student respondent noted;

“... the university has really tried with all the opportunity it has provided the people of Madorawabut still it still falls short of its actual capability in its role as driver and developer of the local economy...”

Most respondents believe that the university is not performing to the best of its abilities with regard to bringing development to the area. The people though, are still appreciative of all the university has done for the people of Madorawaand for that reason they have optimism for the future with regard to their relationship with the university. A staff respondent was of the opinion that:

“... in the future it is expected that the people would reap more benefits than what is currently available. This is because Sokoto State University is still a newly established school and cannot be compared with other older institution, therefore, it is expected that the older Sokoto State University

becomes the more involved it would become in shaping the lives of the people of Madorawa ...”

The foregoing view was shared by the majority of the interviewed respondents who believed that as the university grows older, it would start to pay more attention and exert more influence on its host community development.

Respondents were asked about their views on it they were happy or not about the establishment of Sokoto State University within their community and it had an impact on their views of western education and they were mostly unanimous in their responses, a business owner who was interviewed had this to say;

“... interaction with students of different background has allowed us to understand the value of western education, because of that the value of western education, because of that we have been encouraged to ensure that our children attend school...”

Another student respondent added;

“.... Sokoto State University being established in our community has been well received and most of us are happy with it being here. This has allowed us to understand that western education it used well could be of value to us...”

Here it could be understood that the people feel happy and are in acceptance of the establishment of Sokoto State

University in Madorawa Village and it has also allowed the people to understand the value of western education to the development at their society.

Another indigenous respondent is however of the view that;

“... the relocation of our people from the original land of our ancestors who were the first settlers of the area where the new university was set up, this has unsettled a lot of people, it has also made people deviate from the study of Islam and its teachings which our people have engaged in prior to the establishment of Sokoto State University ...”

This goes to show that although the majority of people are supportive of the university being established that is not the universal view of the people and some are still not happy with the existence of Sokoto State University in Madorawa and the effect it has had on the people.

As noted above the majority of respondents were of the opinion that the location of the university has had a mostly positive effect on the lives of the people. When respondents were probed on how issues like land, culture, religion, economy, politics, health, housing and water supply most had this to say:

“...the Sokoto State Government’s decision to locate the university in our community has made us loose

our ancestral land, but to a certain extent we have been compensated well enough with new land which has turned out to be more valuable than what used to be available before the establishment of the university...

Another indigenous respondent added that;

“... cannot point to any significant change in the culture of the people of Madorawabecause of the existence of Sokoto State University within our community this is because the majority of the people who have come are of the same religion and tribe as us...”

A student respondent had this to say;

“... there has been no visible impact on the religious activities that are carried out in our area; the only difference is that now the amount of people that attend our mosques have increased because of the Sokoto State University staff and students now in our community...”

A staff respondent added that;

“... the economy has been positively impacted and we have experienced growth in most areas of the economy...”

Therefore, from the prior responses, it could be accurately deduced that although Sokoto State University does not have too much of a direct influence

on the socio-economic aspect of Madorawa Village, the influence it exerts nonetheless has a major impact on the lives of the people that live in the village.

The study population for this work are all males, who are all indigenous people of Madorawa Village, who are either employed by Sokoto State University, students of Sokoto State University, or local business owners. This work adopted a purposive sampling method for selecting the participants of the interviews conducted. This was done to gain a better insight into the socio-economic changes which the university has brought about because men are more involved in economic activities than the women in the area.

The study has found that in, line with Arbo (2005), the location of Sokoto State University in their community will definitely bring about rapid socio-economic development. The respondents also noted that, since the establishment of the University all forms of economic activities have flourished while the infrastructure of the community has been growing nonstop since the initial establishment of the university. The people of Madorawahave also had more employment opportunities offered to them, on the basis of qualifications, due to Sokoto State University, this is also in line with Ayobami (1977) who believed that tertiary institutions provide job opportunities for both skilled and unskilled labour and Ekanem et. al (2015) who was of the view that the citing of a tertiary institution in an area

or community would bring changes in economic activities and building conditions. This could be seen as a purposeful intention of the State Government to bring development to Madorawa Village, this is because in a lot of studies that have been carried out all over the globe about the impact of tertiary institutions on their host communities, have shown that any area which hosts any tertiary institution experience changes in their society, this is especially true for rural areas that are not as developed as urban areas as is the case with Sokoto State University and Madorawa Village.

Isola (2017) and Ugwuka (2015) in their works noted that tertiary institutions have roles to play in terms of bringing development to their host communities. In this respect Sokoto State University has already had an impact on Madorawathrough the jobs it has provided to the people of the community and also through an increase in economic activities due to the influx of staff, students and visitors of Sokoto State

University, Although the university has not instituted any direct developmental program its existence alone has caused Madorawa Village to experience a significant growth and development and has begun to transform into a place that is capable of housing the people of the host community and others that they come into contact with as a result of their affiliation with Sokoto State University. In general, the people of Madorawaare happy with the establishment of the University in their community.

In conclusion, the respondents were unanimous in their opinion about the citing of Sokoto State University in their community and they have the belief that the University would have a massive impact on the lives of the people of Madorawaand also their community with the continued socio-economic exchanges that takes place between them and the people who migrate to their community due to the University.

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